

DICHOTOMY OF INTRINSIC MOTIVATION IN ESL CLASSROOM

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Abstract:

Intrinsic motivation is a powerful tool in any language teaching and learning endeavor. Generally, teaching the English language to non- native speakers takes so much effort considering the diverse factors that are inherent in the task and the ineterference of the mother tounge. In a pedagogical vantage point, success in ESL teaching may be possible through learners' own initiative or motivation. Motivation is viewed as the main factor affecting directly or indirectly English language learning and teaching (Gardner, 1985). Conducted in school year 2016-2017, This study ventured on the types of motivation of the foundation students of Oman College of Health Sciences in Sohar City, Sultanate of Oman. A modified and enhanced survey instrument from Gardner's Motivation and Attitude Test Battery instrumented the research flow which was augmented by triangulation method for reliable analysis. Findings revealed that students have closely inter-related motivations for learning English which fell into two major categories, such as: "instrumental" and "integrative". Findings also showed that students are generally "highly" motivated and slightly "instrumentally" motivated to study English. Hence, legitimate improvement strategies and co curricular tasks are recommended to be reinforced either to sustain or redirect the existing motivations.

Keywords: ESL teaching, motivation, integrative, instrumental, L2 acquisition

1. Introduction

Motivation is a vital conduit for ESL teaching and learning. It showcases a clear direction in shaping the future of language education in the global sphere. To date, millions of students around the world are toying on gaining expertise in English as they care to advance in various milieus of life through the knowledge in English language.

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That is by far the essence of motivation according to Gardner (1985) who opined that motivation is the reason for which one strives to acquire a language.

On a larger scale, motivation has been widely accepted by teachers, students and even researchers as a key factor that influences the rate and success of second language (L2) learning. In a study conducted by Locke (1996), it was averred that motivation provides the impetus to initiate second language learning and the factor to sustain the long and often tedious learning process. However, success may depend mainly on the motivational type existing in a learner, but arguably any of the motivational types can turn ESL learners to their fullest. Similarly, Mac Intyre, et al. (2001) provide that motivation type is one of the most appealing yet complex variables used to explain individual differences in language learning. This obviously underscores the need for both ESL teachers and learners to share a synchronized move in aid of translating learning goals into skills and products.

In Oman where English is a secondary if not a tertiary matter to locals, it is still an aspiration to stir the country to become a promising social and political hub that may potentially anchor global affairs by developing young generation and the like to be globally competitive in English. Inspired by neighboring gulf nations' linguistic take off and for other reasons, the government and the private sector have so far jumpstarted hiring caliber ESL teachers from the likes of India, the Philippines, Pakistan, Africa and the native English speaking countries in their effort to put the mission on point not only for Omanis to become employment-ready but also to gain an edge for a global position.

Still, ESL teaching and learning here is not a walk in the park as prominent hurdles often associated with learners' motivation and socio-cultural interference are surfacing despite the integration of bilingualism in universities and colleges (OAAA report 2013). Poor intrinsic motivation is often complained about by teachers as learners tend to lose effort and become victims of their own inaction. Reduced to curiosity, the researchers conducted this research to determine pressing issues attached to student motivation which is viewed by Arnold (2000) as the real deal in any learning process.

2. Research Problems

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of
 - a. gender;
 - b. level in English.
2. What is the overall extent of respondents' intrinsic motivation in the following level?
 - a. integrative;
 - b. instrumental.
3. Which type of motivation is higher in each gender?
4. Is there a significant correlation between English proficiency level of the learners and their integral and instrumental motivation?

3. Review of Literature

Teaching English as second language is a daunting task. It's a tedious process that all elements need to come as one to make the goals translated in the learners. Harry (2007) highlighted that teaching English as a second language may succeed only when the learners begin to realize the life value of the language. On a similar note, learning becomes far easier when learners passion is high and the environment is highly conducive (Lucero 2007). This goes to show how farther can intrinsic motivation take learners beyond the classroom.

Intrinsic motivation, as viewed in a psychological point of view by Gardner (1982), makes an average person learn better than a superior one who learns only for a short term need. Gardner claims that inner behavior defines the solidity of action, putting a person in active and eager disposition. Researchers often stress the role of motivation in learning a second language. In a research conducted by Lennon (1993) at England University of Reading, motivation was cited as the most important single factor influencing continuing development in oral proficiency. Lennon, pointing to Gardner's description of motivation, emphasized that orientation of learners' motivation can fall within either an instrumental or an integrative orientation.

Instrumental orientation is the process by which language is acquired due to the desire to relate to the community where the language is used. On the other hand, **integrative orientation** is treated as a means to meet the goals like scholastic or professional developments, rather than as an objective in itself. It is believed that integrative orientation is more lasting and directly related to success than instrumental orientation which is espoused by Garcia (2007), claiming that learners who are instrumentally motivated tend to be more determined by external aspects like incentives, which is less secure.

In a parallel thought from researchers in different societies, instrumental motivation to learn English has been found to dwell highly among students, believing that it can create them career opportunities and eventually betterment in life. A study in the Philippines, for example, found out that a vast majority of college and university students gear up to acquire a strong command in English to be able to lend in good jobs locally and internationally. This is not actually surprising in a country where media, commerce and external affairs are dominantly delivered in the English language as result of its sincere language policy, much more becoming an integral part of the country's economy as one of the greatest labor exporters due partly to its bilingual efficiency. The same is true in India. Lins (2007) has cited in his study on the same interest similar reasons Indian students hold in pursuing English studies.

However, western researchers have argued the attention being paid to instrumental motivation. Bursall, et. al (1974) discovered that both the integrative and instrumental motivation are contributory to the achievement of second language learners in the United Kingdom. Several studies have come out to share differing thoughts about the effectiveness of both motivations, and seemed creating ripple effect to educators and psychologists who forefront of the social dimension. Challenge arises

further as Gardner (2010) does not argue that integrative motivation is significantly more effective than the other type. He claims more clearly that learners who are integratively motivated has higher likelihood to perform better in language than learners without this orientation. A study in a Singapore university has also provided support to this, as it found valid reasons arising from the nature and conditions of English language teaching and learning in this country. Owing to this fact, Kline (2006) posited major variables affecting the trend like anxiety, self-esteem, and risk taking into consideration Gardner's affective component.

Graham (1997) referring to the language learning theory of Curran (1976), suggests that problems may occur as students are expected to shift to a more independent language uses as they view this as a 'high risk-low gain' scenario. Beebe (1983) argues that learners experience a crisis in motivation because they evaluate the situation as bad gamble. On the same note, ESL students pour less effort when they realize language teaching doesn't suffice their linguistic need and expectations, much more when the environmental element doesn't seem provocative and reinforcing. Al Jawahri (2011) recommends, in this light, that ESL classroom must be given structural emphasis in a way that ESL learners find themselves engaged and active. Thus, he proposes an interactive environment where all members contribute in the learning process.

Second language learning process is subject to numerous external and internal aspects in the society where it exists. Attitude and efficiency of teachers as well as the attitude of learners are among the major aspects of foreign language success in any setting. Klemens (2009) opined that attitude and levels of motivation towards English as a second language are modest, not hindering the learning but also not creating the most excellent environment. In his study, Ellis (1997) pointed out that ESL teachers need to explore more fully the factors that are involved in motivating learners to perform tasks well because it is something they some control over.

Hammer (1991) uses the word goal to categorise the motivation in second language learning into two types: short term goal and long term goal. The former is exemplified when students wish to succeed in doing something in the near future like passing the course or getting a good mark. The latter varies in a way that learners want longer and real benefits for life. In a particular learning situation, students who are less motivated are likely to lose their attention, misbehave and cause discipline problems. whereas, students who are more highly motivated will participate actively and pay more attention to a certain learning task or activity.

Different learners have different motivations to learn English as their second language. In Japan for instance, a study investigating 20 Japanese students revealed that the most common reasons for learning English as a second language were for communication with people overseas, finding employment in high profile career, processing international information, and understanding other cultures. Contrastingly, achievement in the ESL classroom promotes better motivation as found out by Elis (1997) in his study in a French secondary school. This is further espoused by Brophy (1987) pointing to the importance of classroom climate particularly when students feel a

sense of affiliation, being valued and respected, consequently, they are more likely to engage actively in the learning process. Relatively, Clement (2006) assessed Hungarian students' motivation to learn English and revealed the presence of a comparatively classroom motivation.

Strategies, methods, approaches and course materials are deemed significant in learners' motivation. According to Lile (2009), these must also be relevant to the students. He suggests using vocabulary that the students can relate to and material they would find interesting. Lile recommends another very important part of proper classroom instruction to keep a low affective filter is to keep it simple and structural. Harris (2008) also proposes that teachers need to be caring as this is another intrinsic motivation of students. He says that teachers should consider student lapses on grammar and related linguistic aspects as rather a springboard for incidental instruction rather than as ground for lowering marks. Harris points to the importance of corrective feedback mechanism which supposes the way to be less emotional dampening.

Increased parental awareness is also crucial to a child's motivation (Bantjes, 2011). To support motivation, parents must participate actively in the student's life. The same set of goals and practices at school that promote motivation should be followed at home. If they are not also followed at home, it could dilute classroom efforts. Through appropriate parent/teacher/student communication, everyone can understand what is expected from each other, and the student will see that everyone involved cares about his/her academic success.

Positive attitude is a must for a successful learning atmosphere. To promote self-confidence, it helps if the teacher is self-confident. Positive approval and praise for student efforts is very effective, even if the student is wrong. Positive energy affirming a belief in the students' ability develops a comfortable atmosphere for the students in the classroom (Mendez, 2008).

4. Significance of the Study

Since intrinsic motivation enables access to the educative process, this study provides ESL teachers bulk of information as leverage to efficiently carry out teaching goals for the ESL learners. Centrally anchored on fresh facts, this takes them closely to the intrinsic aspects of teaching the English language in a non- native context, and help them strategize methodologies and techniques that aid delivery and reinforcement in ESL classrooms. This also provides ESL curriculum planners and leaders a platform to integrate realistic approaches, processes and instructional materials to tickle learners' linguistic interest towards second language acquisition. Finally, it adds up to the wide array of knowledge and literature on motivation for researchers of the same research interest.

5. Research Methodology

5.1 Respondents

The respondents of the study were 35 students of the Foundation Center of Oman College of Health Sciences in Sohar, Oman. These students were currently enrolled in English Level 2 and Level 3 during the second trimester of school year 2016-2017. They were chosen as the respondents using the total enumeration purposive sampling. Table 1 presents the respondents of the study.

Table 1: Population of the study

Respondents	Level 2	Percent	Level 3	Percent	Total
Male	8	22.85	3	8.57	11
Female	18	51.43	6	17.14	24
Total	26	74.28	9	25.71	35

It is seen from the table that level 2 has a total population of 26 students with 8 males and 18 females. Level three on the other hand has a total of 9 students with 3 males and 6 females. Both level 2 and 3 has 11 boys and 24 girls totaling to 35 respondents.

5.2 Research Instrument

The researchers used a questionnaire which was adopted from Prappal's Attitude Testing to elicit information on learners' motivation. The questionnaire composed of 20 attitudinal statements sub-categorized into instrumental and integrative motivation. Preliminaries of the questionnaire include basic profile of the respondents, such as: gender, and English proficiency level. The instrument was no longer subjected to dry-run validation since it was totally adopted from Prappal's Attitude Testing which is already considered valid and reliable.

5.3 Data Collection

The researchers oriented the respondents before having them answer the questionnaire. This data gathering instrument was distributed during the respondents' self study hour within the supervision of the researchers. Some indicators in the questionnaire had to be explained as the respondents hardly understood them. The questionnaire was administered for utmost 20 to 30 minutes.

5.4 Data Analysis

Gathered data from the questionnaires were tabulated and analysed using the SPSS software version 20. The Pearson correlation was used to determine the relationship of gender to the type of motivation as well as the relationship of English Proficiency level to the type of motivation.

The needed weighted means were also computed to determine the level of motivation by the respondents in each indicator of motivation.

6. Discussion of Findings

This chapter presents the results and discussion of the study.

Table 2: Respondents' level of intrinsic motivation in terms of integrative and instrumental type of motivation

Integrative			Instrumental		
Indicators	w.m.	D.E.	Indicators	w.m.	D.E.
1. Studying English Enables me understand English books, movies, pop music etc.	2.5714	H	1. I mainly focus on using English for class.	2.3714	H
2. Studying English enables me to better understand and appreciate the ways of life of native speakers.	2.2571	M	2. I simply quote the textbook and do not really communicate myself when speaking or writing in class.	2.2286	M
3. Studying English enables me to discuss interesting topics in English with the people from other national backgrounds.	2.3714	H	3. I am interested in reading only English textbooks for my university study , but not other English texts e.g. periodicals, magazines.	2.2286	M
4. Studying English enables me to keep in touch with foreign acquaintances.	2.2857	H	4. I am more interested in earning a university degree and a good job than learning English language itself.	2.2857	H
5. Studying English enables me to transfer my knowledge to other people e.g giving directions to tourist and teaching youngsters.	2.6	H	5. I am more interested in furthering my higher education than learning English itself.	2.2	M
6. Studying English enables me to participate freely in academic, social, and professional activities among other cultural groups.	2.4	H	6. Learning English is important for travelling abroad.	2.6286	H
7. Studying English enables me to appreciate English arts and literature.	2.2857	H	7. Learning English is important for making me knowledgeable and skillful person.	2.6857	H
8. Studying English enables me to behave like native speakers.	2.4	H	8. Learning English is important for making me an educated person	2.7143	H
9. Studying English helps me to be open minded and sociable person like English speaking people.	2.3143	H	9. Being proficient in English can lead to more success and achievements in life.	2.3143	H
10. I am determined to study English as best as i can to achieve maximum proficiency.	2.6	H	10. Being proficient in English makes the people respect me.	2.0857	M
mean	2.4086	H		2.3743	H

Legend: H – highly motivated; M – moderately motivated; L – low motivated

Of the ten indicators for integrative motivation, nine of which were viewed by the respondents as high motivation. The only indicator perceived as moderate motivation as indicated by its weighted mean of 2.2571 is the second statement saying that "*studying English enables me to better understand and appreciate the ways of life of native*

speakers." As per overall level of motivation, the respondents feel that integrative motivation is highly motivating in learning English.

Likewise, the instrumental type of motivation was also considered by the students as highly motivating in learning English as shown by the group mean of 2.3743. However, out of the ten indicators, three of which were perceived as moderately motivating. The first indicator stating that *"I simply quote the textbook and do not really communicate myself when speaking or writing in class"* and the second stating that *"I am interested in reading only English textbooks for my university study, but not other English texts e.g. periodicals, magazines"* showed exactly the same mean of 2.2286 interpreted as moderately motivating. The indicator stating that *"I am more interested in furthering my higher education than learning English itself"* is the third one that was considered as moderately motivating with a mean of 2.2.

Table 3: Level of motivation in terms of gender

Integrative			Instrumental		
Indicators	Mean (Male)	Mean (Female)	Indicators	Mean (Male)	Mean (Female)
1. Studying English Enables me understand English books, movies, pop music etc.	2.5455	2.5833	1. I mainly focus on using English for class.	2.1818	2.4583
2. Studying English enables me to better understand and appreciate the ways of life of native speakers.	1.9091	2.4167	2. I simply quote the textbook and do not really communicate myself when speaking or writing in class.	2.2727	2.2083
3. Studying English enables me to discuss interesting topics in English with the people from other national backgrounds.	2	2.5417	3. I am interested in reading only English textbooks for my university study, but not other English texts e.g. periodicals, magazines.	2	2.3333
4. Studying English enables me to keep in touch with foreign acquaintances.	1.9091	2.4583	4. I am more interested in earning a university degree and a good job than learning English language itself.	2.4545	2.2083
5. Studying English enables me to transfer my knowledge to other people e.g giving directions to tourist and teaching youngsters.	2.4545	2.6667	5. I am more interested in furthering my higher education than learning English itself.	2	2.2917
6. Studying English enables me to participate freely in academic, social, and professional activities among other cultural groups.	2.1818	2.5	6. Learning English is important for travelling abroad.	2.4545	2.7083
7. Studying English enables me to appreciate English arts and literature.	1.8182	2.5	7. Learning English is important for making me knowledgeable and skillful	2.5455	2.75

			person.		
8. Studying English enables me to behave like native speakers.	2.1818	2.5	8. Learning English is important for making me an educated person.	2.4545	2.8333
9. Studying English helps me to be open minded and sociable person like English speaking people.	1.9091	2.5	9. Being proficient in English can lead to more success and achievements in life.	1.9091	2.5
10. I am determined to study English as best as i can to achieve maximum proficiency.	2.5455	2.625	10. Being proficient in English makes the people respect me.	1.8182	2.2083
mean	2.1455	2.5292		2.2091	2.45

Legend: H – highly motivated; M – moderately motivated; L – low motivated

Table 3 presents the level of motivation of the respondents in terms of gender. The table shows that male students find integrative type of motivation as moderately motivating for them in learning English as indicated by their group mean of 2.1455. The female students however, find integrative type of motivation to be highly motivating when it comes to learning English as evident by their group mean of 2.5292.

With regards to the instrumental type of motivation, the male respondents had the same level of motivation to that of integrative motivation. The males' group mean of 2.2091 show that they consider instrumental motivation to be moderately motivating when learning English. On the other hand, the females' perception about instrumental motivation is highly motivating as indicated by their group mean of 2.45.

Table 3.a: Relationship between gender and the type of intrinsic motivation

Correlations				
		Gender	Integrative Mean	Instrumental mean
Gender	Pearson Correlation	1	.533**	.375*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001	.026
	N	35	35	35
Integrative mean	Pearson Correlation	.533**	1	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001		.009
	N	35	35	35
Instrumental mean	Pearson Correlation	.375*	.433**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.026	.009	
	N	35	35	35
**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).				
*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).				

Table 3.a presents the result of Pearson Correlation computation using the SPSS version 20 software. Results show that there is a significant relationship between gender and integrative type of motivation as revealed by the computed probability value of .001 which is less than the set significant level of 0.05. However, the extent of relationship is moderate as indicated by the computed r-value of 0.533.

The Instrumental type of motivation on the other hand, is also significantly related to gender as shown by the probability value of 0.026 which is lesser than the 0.05 level of significance. However, the degree of relationship is very weak as suggested by the r-value of 0.375.

These findings imply that male students would like to learn English because of Intrinsic motivation while the female students will learn English because of Instrumental motivation or vice versa. Meaning, the preferred type of motivation in learning English by the male students is different from that of female's type of motivation in learning English. This could be supported by the difference in level of motivation according to gender in Table 3 wherein the level of Intrinsic motivation for the male is moderate (group mean = 2.1455) while high (Group mean = 2.5292) motivation for the female. Similar with the Instrumental motivation wherein the male respondents consider the Instrumental motivation as moderate (Group mean = 2.2091) while the female respondents consider it as high (group mean = 2.45) motivation.

Table 4 presents the students' level of motivation when they were group according to their English Proficiency level. It is seen from the table that level two students viewed the integrative type of motivation as highly (group mean = 2.365) motivating which is similar to that of level 3 who also perceived integrative motivation as highly (group mean = 2.533) motivating.

Table 4: Level of motivation according the respondents' English Proficiency level

Integrative			Instrumental		
Indicators	Mean (Level2)	Mean (Level 3)	Indicators	Mean (Level 2)	Mean (Level 3)
1. Studying English Enables me understand English books, movies, pop music etc.	2.538-H	2.666-H	1. I mainly focus on using English for class.	2.538-H	1.888-M
2. Studying English enables me to better understand and appreciate the ways of life of native speakers.	2.076-M	2.777-H	2. I simply quote the textbook and do not really communicate myself when speaking or writing in class.	2.307-M	2.0-M
3. Studying English enables me to discuss interesting topics in English with the people from other national backgrounds.	2.2308-M	2.777-H	3. I am interested in reading only English textbooks for my university study , but not other English texts e.g. periodicals, magazines.	2.346-H	1.888-M
4. Studying English enables me to keep in touch with foreign acquaintances.	2.2692-M	2.333-M	4.I am more interested in earning a university degree and a good job than learning English language itself.	2.384-H	2.0-M
5. Studying English enables me to transfer my knowledge to other people e.g giving directions to tourist and	2.538-H	2.777-H	5. I am more interested in furthering my higher education than	2.307-M	1.888-M

teaching youngsters.			learning English itself.		
6. Studying English enables me to participate freely in academic, social, and professional activities among other cultural groups.	2.346-H	2.555-H	6. Learning English is important for travelling abroad.	2.538-H	2.888-H
7. Studying English enables me to appreciate English arts and literature.	2.269-M	2.333-M	7. Learning English is important for making me knowledgeable and skillful person.	2.615-H	2.888-H
8. studying English enables me to behave like native speakers.	2.5-H	2.111-M	8. Learning English is important for making me an educated person.	2.653-H	2.888-H
9. Studying English helps me to be open minded and sociable person like English speaking people.	2.307-M	2.333-M	9. Being proficient in English can lead to more success and achievements in life.	2.192-M	2.666-H
10. I am determined to study English as best as i can to achieve maximum proficiency.	2.576-H	2.666-H	10. Being proficient in English makes the people respect me.	2.076-M	2.111-M
mean	2.365-H	2.533-H		2.396-H	2.311-M

Speaking of instrumental motivation, the level 2 students consider it as highly motivating with a group mean of 2.396 while the level 3 group find it as moderately motivating with the group mean of 2.311.

Table 4.a: Relationship of English proficiency level to the type of intrinsic motivation

Correlations				
		Proflevel	Integrative Mean	Instrumental mean
Proflevel	Pearson Correlation	1	.220	-.125
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.205	.475
	N	35	35	35
Integrative mean	Pearson Correlation	.220	1	.433**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.205		.009
	N	35	35	35
Instrumental mean	Pearson Correlation	-.125	.433**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.475	.009	
	N	35	35	35

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.a presents the computed values of Pearson correlation using the SPSS version 20 software. Results show that there is no significant relationship between English proficiency level and integrative type of motivation as revealed by the computed probability value of 0.205 which is greater than the significant level of 0.05. The same is true with the Instrumental type of motivation wherein it has no significant relationship to English proficiency level.

These findings imply that students' English proficiency level has nothing to do on which type of motivation each group may prefer. This is supported by the computed group mean in table 4 which all mean fall under high motivation.

7. Conclusion and Recommendations

Motivation factors in the development of second language in any learner. Though, the amount of intrinsic motivation a learner pours in the learning process may or may not favor the development. In the study at hand, two types of intrinsic motivation - integrative and instrumental- are evidently a high motivation with an equal impact to students' learning of the English course regardless of gender and proficiency. Some students have varying reasons towards learning the second language and intend to be proficient in it for their own special reasons .

Unfortunately, there have been few studies conducted to investigate on the motivation of Omanis in learning English. It would therefore make sense for Omani teachers to propose instructional methods that enhance motivation to learn English based on the context of the Omani society without prejudicing international standards. Somehow, this research would clarify or intensify appreciation on the behavior, purpose and reason of Omani students in learning English which in turn provides a better segway to teachers to engage more meaningfully with the educative process.

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